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THE IMPACT OF SMART GRID TECHNOLOGIES ON DECARBONIZATION AND INCREASING ENERGY EFFICIENCY OF ELECTRIC POWER SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the environmental aspects of implementing the Smart Grid concept in the context of the global transition to low-carbon and sustainable energy. It analyzes the impact of Smart Grid technologies on reducing greenhouse gas emissions, increasing energy efficiency, and expanding the integration of renewable energy sources into the energy system. It demonstrates that the use of intelligent control systems and digital technologies contributes to the optimization of electricity generation, transmission, and distribution processes, which, in turn, reduces energy costs for industrial consumers and improves the reliability and quality of power supply. Furthermore, the development of smart energy infrastructure and the digitalization of the energy sector create the preconditions for the creation of new high-tech jobs and the sustainable development of the energy sector.

Keywords: Smart Grid, environmental impact, carbon emissions, energy efficiency, renewable energy sources, operating costs, energy infrastructure, energy system integration.

INTRODUCTION

Amid global initiatives to reduce pollution and increase greenhouse gas emissions, countries around the world are actively implementing environmentally

sustainable technologies. According to the US National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL), industrial and energy companies face significant challenges adapting to changing environmental conditions and increasingly stringent regulatory requirements. Projections indicate a potential increase in carbon emissions in the US from 1.7 billion tons in 2025 to 2.3 billion tons by 2030. However, according to NREL research, the implementation of comprehensive energy efficiency programs and the large-scale integration of renewable energy sources can not only slow this growth but also reduce carbon emissions to less than 1 billion tons by 2030, thereby contributing to a more sustainable and environmentally friendly energy system.

MAIN PART

Environmental effects from the implementation of Smart Grid technologies:

1. Reducing carbon emissions - Smart Grid technologies contribute to significant reductions in carbon emissions. The key mechanisms for achieving this include:

- **demand and load management**, optimizing the use of electricity and minimizing the consumption of expensive peak electricity generated by less efficient power units;

- improving energy efficiency, implementing educational programs and adaptive tariff systems contributes to more rational use of energy by consumers;

- Reducing the variability of renewable energy sources, integrating and optimising energy sources such as wind and solar reduces fluctuations in their performance;

- Integration of electric vehicles and distributed energy sources, the inclusion of electric vehicles and distributed energy sources in the energy system contributes to a more even distribution of energy and a reduction in dependence on carbon-intensive sources.

According to a report by the International Energy Agency (IEA), the use of Smart Grid technologies can reduce carbon emissions by an average of 10-20% in the long term through improved energy management, more efficient use of renewable energy sources, and reduced energy losses.

2. Reduction of operating and maintenance costs

in the energy sector. Key areas of savings include:

- reducing the frequency of emergency response and diagnostics; automated systems allow for prompt troubleshooting and minimizing costs for emergency calls and diagnostics;

- transition to condition-based maintenance, the use of real-time monitoring technologies allows for maintenance based on the actual condition of the equipment, which reduces costs compared to scheduled maintenance;

- Reducing the risk of equipment overload. Real-time information on the condition of network assets helps prevent overloads and potential equipment failures, especially for critical components such as transformers. Using smart sensors can reduce transformer maintenance costs by 25-30%.

- Optimizing power distribution, Smart Grid technologies can reduce power losses by more than 30% by improving power plant performance and managing the balance of the power system.

3. Reducing costs for industrial consumers,

Commercial and industrial consumers also benefit from the implementation of Smart Grid technologies. Examples of savings include:

- Electric motor efficiency, high-efficiency motors, and variable-speed drives can significantly reduce energy consumption. Using such motors can save up to 85 billion kWh per year;

- automation of responses to price signals, drives can automatically adjust energy consumption in response to price signals, which reduces energy costs and has a positive impact on social benefits.

4. Improving the quality of service for business clients,

Smart Grid technologies help improve the quality of service for business clients by:

- automatic monitoring and maintenance, the ability to automatically monitor and actively maintain consumer equipment helps achieve energy saving and carbon emission reduction goals;

Data transparency and recommendations, two-way communication, and improved metering systems enable energy companies to provide recommendations for energy optimization. EPRI estimates that this could lead to annual energy savings of between 2.2 and 8.8 billion kWh.

5. Impact on jobs and economic development:

- The creation of new jobs, development, implementation, and maintenance of Smart Grid technologies create new jobs in fields such as engineering, IT, data analytics, and energy system maintenance. This also stimulates the development of new startups and innovative companies;

- Economic development and the implementation of smart grids contribute to economic growth by increasing the efficiency and competitiveness of the energy sector. Optimizing energy costs and reducing losses contribute to more stable electricity prices and increased economic attractiveness for investors.

Table 1.
Smart Grid Value Chain

Value chain	Business effect	Recipient of value	Value received	Benefits
Final consumption - all actions taken by consumers, or the customer's location	Full satisfaction of the requirements of each individual consumer	Consumers of electrical energy	1. Information on individual demand and consumption. 2. Possibility of increasing the capacity of network sections.	1. Possibility of optimizing energy management. 2. Increasing the availability of the distributed generation equipment network
Real-time dispatch control	1. Improvement of traditional measurement systems. 2. Increasing the system's resilience (ability to withstand a shock and continue to operate)	Dispatchers	1. Loss management - fault location, diagnostic information on demand. 2. Information on the equipment status, including repair information in real time. 3. Load balancing	1. Optimized administrative management system (OMS) (DA working with GIS, GPS, mobile messaging). 2. Dispatchers focus only on significant deviations in the operation of a self-healing network and spend less time troubleshooting problems
Asset Operation - Day-to-day operations to ensure network reliability	1. Reducing asset life cycle costs. 2. Maximizing value from existing networks and generation	Asset managers, operations and maintenance personnel	1. Reliable and reliable information on the state of assets. 2. Real-time information on the completion of troubleshooting and scheduled work	1. Focus more on data analysis than on data collection. 2. Ability to validate the effectiveness of asset management programs. 3. Reducing the level of technological risk
Asset creation - reconstruction and new construction of assets	Managing the workforce with a focus on worker and consumer safety	Labor resources (internal and contractors)	Real-time status of the configuration in use	1. Higher design efficiency due to simpler design. 2. Introduction of work safety guarantees
Asset Development Design - Identifying the location, conditions, and requirements for replacement or new	1. Achieving service availability and delivery goals. 2. Reduction of maintenance and supply costs. 3. Efficiency and environmental friendliness	Designers of services, substations and electrical distribution systems	1. Design based on IP protocol data, on-site drawings. 2. Virtual discussion of ideas, design in real conditions	1. Go plug & play. 2. Reducing the need for labor

construction of Smart Grid assets				
Production, transmission, distribution and storage of electricity purchased from distributed generation	1. Reduction of restrictions in electricity generation. 2. Profitability for external suppliers	Internal and external suppliers of distributed generation	1. Infrastructure for connecting domestic supplies to the grid of energy supply companies	1. The ability to easily connect to the network of available distributed energy sources. 2. Simplicity and cost-effectiveness of electricity supply
Strategic planning and development - a long-term overview of customer needs and systems for making investment decisions	1. Availability and reliability through investment optimization. 2. Achieving shareholders' expectations regarding the level of profitability	Investors, top management	Information about the system's operation: required at a specific moment and specific (object-specific)	1. Shifting the focus of efforts from data collection to data analysis. 2. Possibility of introducing innovative system modeling and conducting research on loss reduction. 3. Optimization of asset management

This table illustrates how the implementation of the Smart Grid concept brings specific benefits at different levels of the value chain, providing both operational and strategic benefits to various stakeholders.

Overall, the effects and benefits for business achieved through the implementation of the Smart Grid concept can take various forms:

- a safer production process due to increased reliability of power supply;
- increasing the level of customer satisfaction;
- increase in sales volumes due to improved levels of customer service;
- reduction of production costs due to reduction of downtime due to failures in the power system;
- reduction of the level of use of non-renewable energy sources;
- creation of new jobs and potential GDP growth;
- the opportunity to modernize the energy system based on the integration of energy assets in the field of generation, transmission, distribution and storage of electric energy.

Research conducted abroad shows that the multifaceted effects of the implementation of the Smart Grid concept for all stakeholders reaches its maximum only in the case of the combined implementation of all properties, methodology and elements of the new technological basis; individual components, technologies and devices are considered as a complex (system) of interacting elements that provide the required functional properties, the choice of composition and level of which, in turn, is determined by the user.

CONCLUSION

The implementation of the Smart Grid concept represents a significant step toward creating a sustainable and efficient energy system that significantly reduces environmental impacts and carbon emissions. The implementation of Smart Grid technologies optimizes energy management, integrates renewable energy sources, improves energy efficiency, and reduces operating costs, resulting in significant environmental and economic benefits. Importantly, it also improves customer service, creates new jobs, and stimulates economic growth. The use of these technologies not only contributes to environmental sustainability but also enhances the reliability and security of energy systems, ensuring the long-term sustainability and development of energy infrastructure. Overall, the comprehensive implementation of Smart Grid technologies offers numerous benefits, encompassing both operational and strategic objectives for all participants in the energy chain.

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